

Management of Acute Pain in Cancer

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ABSTRACT Acute Pain conditions that a cancer patient may experience are; acute pain crises, breakthrough pain, postoperative/procedural pain, or acute pain because of bone involvement or malignant bowel obstruction, and chemotherapy or radiotherapy induced mucositis. Some of the important and commonly presented conditions are discussed in this article.

KEYWORDS Acute pain, cancer

Introduction

The World Health Organization (WHO) reported that out of 28 million people living with cancer, about 5.5 million received no effective treatment for their cancer pain [13]. Overall about a third of those on cancer treatment and up to 80% of terminally ill with cancer experience pain [9].

Cancer patients frequently develop acute pain sometimes as a result of treatment interventions such as surgery, chemotherapy, hormonal therapy, and radiotherapy [2]. Also, the spread of cancer into body organs often generates acute pain, for example, pathological or microfracture, spinal cord or nerve compression, visceral obstruction [2]. Both acute and chronic cancer pain can be nociceptive, neuropathic or mixed nociceptive-neuropathic nature [2].

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Assessment of acute cancer pain:

A cancer patient with acute pain requires urgent assessment and treatment. Assessment should include a full history and examination, and it should be performed by using appropriate

tools, and appropriate investigations to determine the presence of recurrent disease or serious complications of cancer that might require active interventions [13].

Both the intensity of pain and impact of pain on function should be assessed individually. Visual analogue scales (VASs), numerical rating scales (NRSs) from 0 to 10 and verbal rating scales are all commonly used to record the intensity of pain [13]. The Brief Pain Inventory (BPI) or McGill Pain Questionnaire is useful for assessment of the impact of pain on function, e.g. sleep [3]. For patients who are cognitively impaired, assessment of pain based on related behaviours (e.g., groaning, frowning, crying out and agitation) or collateral history from carers is appropriate; however, there are also specific tools available (e.g., Abbey Pain Scale [13].

Acute postoperative pain management of cancer patients on long-term opioid:

Majority of the cancer patients undergoing surgical interventions are on long-term and often high-dose opioids and are, therefore, have to be regarded as opioid tolerant. Two important management considerations of these patients are the provision of good pain management and the prevention of opioid withdrawal in the perioperative period [14]. To prevent opioid withdrawal, a continuation of the previous opioid at established doses as a background medication is the best approach. Equi-analgesic doses of opioids should be prescribed for patients who will not be able to tolerate oral intake in the postoperative period [15].

Multimodal analgesia strategies are more important in cancer patients than in any other patient populations (Schug, 2012). Such multimodal strategies should include the use of non-opioid analgesics such as paracetamol and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs/selective COX-2 inhibitors (NSAIDs/COXIBS) to provide a background of the non-opioid

analgesic cover. Whenever possible regional anaesthesia techniques, in particular by peripheral nerve or epidural catheters, should be a component of pain management. Also, the perioperative use of alpha-2-delta subunit modulators (gabapentin or pregabalin) including a premedication with these drugs should be considered. Gabapentinoids only improve analgesia and reduce opioid requirements, but they might also play a role in the reduction of opioid-induced hyperalgesia [5].

Another component of multimodal analgesia with good evidence in the setting of the opioid-tolerant patient is the NMDA receptor ketamine; an intra-operative loading dose followed by a low-dose continuous infusion has shown significant benefits in opioid-tolerant patients [12].

Opioid tolerant patients generally require higher opioid doses in the perioperative period than opioid-naïve patients [12]; the increased requirements ranged between 30% and 300% in some studies [4]. Titration of opioid doses ideally in the form of patient-controlled analgesia (PCA) is the most appropriate technique. However, the bolus dose in such patients needs to be increased for the technique to be effective. The background infusion might be needed in cancer patients which is generally not recommended for opioid-naïve patients [15].

Persistent Post-Surgical Pain (PPSP) in cancer patients:

Cancer patients undergoing surgical procedures are at increased risk of developing PPSP. It is estimated that out of those who suffered PPSP, 5–10% experienced severe pain that seriously affects their health-related quality of life [10]. Although no definite causative factors are known, however, some risk factors for PPSP in cancer patients have been identified such as chemotherapy, radiotherapy and prior opioid use [12]. The most accepted explanation is that persistent pain after surgery is often the result of nerve injury with subsequent central sensitisation in response to this trauma [11].

There is some evidence that specific anaesthetic techniques reduce the incidence of PPSP. A recent surprise finding of this issue was that the use of nitrous oxide as a compound of inhalational anaesthesia reduces the incidence by around 50% [7]; this is currently the subject of further study. Also, there are some studies and a recent meta-analysis, which support the notion that regional anaesthetic techniques such as spinal or epidural anaesthesia and regional analgesic techniques after surgery have a beneficial effect on persistent post-surgical pain [1]. The data are particularly convincing with the use of epidural anaesthesia and analgesia for thoracotomy with an odds ratio of 0.33 and with the use of paravertebral blockade for breast cancer surgery with an odds ratio of 0.37 [1].

Furthermore, there is increasing evidence, that the perioperative use of gabapentinoids, in particular, pregabalin, not only improve postoperative pain control but is also a protection from the development of persistent post-surgical pain [8]. However, the literature in this area is still limited and more comprehensive and systematic research is needed to further the development of preventive treatment options here.

Management of breakthrough pain:

Breakthrough pain is a transitory flare-up of pain in the setting of chronic cancer pain managed with opioid drugs [12]. It may occur four times a day lasting for few minutes to half an hour as a result of waning of opioid effect (end-of-dose failure) or could be precipitated by some movements or events (incident pain) [12].

The same drug usually manages breakthrough pain as in the slow-release preparation, given as an immediate-release preparation in a dose of around one-sixth of the daily dose [6] or an available short-acting formulation when on a patch. Transmucosal and intranasal fentanyl preparations are another options for treatment, as they show rapid onset and short duration of effect [2]; the most commonly available preparations are oral transmucosal fentanyl lozenges.

Acute Pain Crises:

Acute pain crises are defended as the severe uncontrolled pain causing distress for the patient, family members or both [12]. It is a medical emergency that requires prompt management. Rapid analgesia may be provided with regular dose parenteral opioid or the use of patient-controlled analgesia (PCA) [12].

Conclusion

Cancer patient frequently develops acute pain episodes despite taking an opioid analgesic for chronic pain. It is important to consider these patients as opioid tolerant so that appropriate dosage can be titrated to produce the desired effect. A multimodal analgesia strategy with background continuation of long-term therapy is the best approach.

References

1. ANDREAE, M. H. & ANDREAE, D. A. 2013. Regional anaesthesia to prevent chronic pain after surgery: a Cochrane systematic review and meta-analysis. *British Journal of Anaesthesia*, 111, 711-720.
2. AURET, K. & SCHUG, S. A. 2013. Pain management for the cancer patient - current practice and future developments. *Best Pract Res Clin Anaesthesiol*, 27, 545-61.
3. BREIVIK, H., BORCHGREVINK, P. C., ALLEN, S. M., ROSSELAND, L. A., ROMUNDSTAD, L., HALS, E. K., KVARSTEIN, G. & STUBHAUG, A. 2008. Assessment of pain. *Br J Anaesth*, 101, 17-24.
4. C. A. HUXTABLE, L. J. R., A. A. SOMOGYI, P. E. MACINTYRE 2011. Acute pain management in opioid-tolerant patients- a growing challenge. *Anaesth Intensive Care*, 39, 804-823.
5. CARACENI, A., ZECCA, E., BONEZZI, C., ARCURI, E., TUR, R. Y., MALTONI, M., VISENTIN, M., GORNI, G., MARTINI, C. & TIRELLI, W. 2004. Gabapentin for neuropathic cancer pain: a randomized controlled trial from the Gabapentin Cancer Pain Study Group. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, 22, 2909-2917.
6. CASUCCIO, A., MERCADANTE, S. & FULFARO, F. 2009. Treatment strategies for cancer patients with breakthrough pain. *Expert Opinion on Pharmacotherapy*, 10, 947-953.
7. CHAN, M. T. V., WAN, A. C. M., GIN, T., LESLIE, K. & MYLES, P. S. 2011. Chronic postsurgical pain after nitrous oxide anesthesia. *PAIN*, 152, 2514-2520.
8. CLARKE, H., BONIN, R. P., ORSER, B. A., ENGLESAKIS, M., WIJEYSUNDERA, D. N. & KATZ, J. 2012. The Prevention of Chronic Postsurgical Pain Using Gabapentin and Pregabalin: A Combined Systematic Review and

Meta-Analysis. *Anesthesia & Analgesia*, 115, 428-442
10.1213/ANE.0b013e318249d36e.

9. JON RAPHAEL, J. H., SAM AHMEDZAI, JANETTE BARRIE, PAUL FARQUHAR-SMITH, JOHN WILLIAMS, CATHERINE URCH, MICHAEL I. BENNETT, KAREN ROBB, BRIAN SIMPSON, MAX PITTLER, BARBARA WIDER, CHARLIE EWER-SMITH, JAMES DECOURCY, ANN YOUNG, CHRISTINA LIOSSI, RENEE MCCULLOUGH, DILINI RAJAPAKSE, MARTIN JOHNSON, RUI DUARTE, AND ELIZABETH SPARKES, 2010. Cancer Pain-Part 2- Physical, Interventional and Complimentary Therapies; Management in the Community; Acute, Treatment-Related and Complex Cancer Pain- A Perspective from the British Pain Society Endorsed by the UK Association. *Pain Medicine*, 11, 872-896.
10. JONES, I. & BARI, F. 2014. Chronic pain after surgery. *Surgery (Oxford)*, 32, 93-96.
11. KEHLET, H., JENSEN, T. S. & WOOLF, C. J. 2006. Persistent postsurgical pain: risk factors and prevention. *The Lancet*, 367, 1618-1625.
12. MACINTYRE PE, S. S., SCOTT DA, ET AL 2010. Acute pain management: scientific evidence. Melbourne: ANZCA & FPM.
13. RIPAMONTI, C. I., SANTINI, D., MARANZANO, E., BERTI, M. & ROILA, F. 2012. Management of cancer pain: ESMO Clinical Practice Guidelines. *Annals of Oncology*, 23, vii139-vii154.
14. SCHUG, S. A. 2012a. Acute pain management in the opioid-tolerant patient. *Pain Management*, 2, 581-591.
15. SCHUG, S. A. 2012b. Acute pain management in the opioid-tolerant patient. *Pain Management*, 2, 581-591.